

Automatic Agriculture monitoring system

Sujathakumari B A
Dept of Electronics
and
Communication Engineering,
SJCE, JSS Science and
Technology University, Mysuru,
India.

Rakshith kumar M
Dept of Electronics
and
Communication Engineering,
SJCE, JSS Science and
Technology University, Mysuru,
India.

Raghunandana V Mulgund
Dept of Electronics
and
Communication Engineering SJCE, JSS
Science and Technology University,
Mysuru, India.

Received: May 20, 2025

Accepted: Jun 18, 2025

Published: Jun 25, 2025

Abstract—For maximizing the crop yield while conserving water and energy the precision in irrigation plays a very important role. This project automatic agriculture monitoring system led by a logic-based algorithm which will ensure that the water is delivered only when and where it is needed. The system will monitor real time soil moisture data and makes irrigation decisions based on predefined threshold values. When the soil moisture goes below the limit which is set, it activates the irrigation process once the suitable level of moisture is restored the system automatically stops watering. The fully automated decision making process which leads to increase the accuracy and minimizing human participation. The model is designed to operate with minimal resources, including solar energy, which suitable for both rural and off-grid agriculture settings. The main strength of this project lies in its precise algorithmic control, which enhances the use of water efficiently, maintains the ideal soil conditions, and supports sustainable and scalable farming practices

Keywords— Smart Agriculture, Automated Irrigation, Soil Moisture Sensor, Arduino, Solar-Powered System, Precision Farming, IoT in Agriculture, Water Conservation

I. INTRODUCTION

Precision in agriculture field plays a very important role in reducing the losses. modern agriculture involves the advance technology which helps to reduce the man power. the microcontrollers and sensors carries the work in a good manner which enhance the productivity and agriculture security. the responsiveness given by the embedded system components helps to build the entire system which is efficient and less expensive helps to reduce the agriculture wastages, power wastage, and to reduce the time consumption. The microcontrollers like Arduino helps to establish contact with the sensors and processors in a feasible way. The technology in the field of agriculture helps most of the farmer in the surveillance system. controlling the water pump helps for the better utilization of water which maintain the plants health in all the season so it reduces the human intervention. the solar powered project helps to gets the energy so the expenses is reduces. In this generation it is not easy to pay wages for the people for the agriculture works where most of the works get controlling by the embedded systems. the temperature and humidity sensors will helps to provide real time data so the farmers can make planning of planting seeds, fertilizing,

watering and harvesting. The watering is a important work to provide based on the soil condition whether it is dry or wet. if its too wet the plants cannot withstand. some plants always needs water to live so this project helps for the productivity as in case of any agriculture plantation. the maintainance and installation, servicing, replacement of these components easy easier and less expensive. The optimized algorithm helps to achieve accuracy in the process of work so the stress for the farmers gets reduce.

II. RELATED WORKS

The evolution of smart agriculture has emphasized the development of precise and accurate systems for sustainable resource management. In the domain of smart indoor farming Kariyenye et al. [1] conducted a statistical study on rainfall variability and its effect on tomato production, offering accurate planning insights for small-scale farmers. Setiawan et al. [2] developed a solar-powered IoT monitoring system for smart farming, ensuring precise data acquisition and improved energy utilization. Yahaya et al. [3] analyzed tomato productivity under different soil amendments through controlled field experiments to ensure accurate comparisons. Shamsihr et al. [4] reviewed automation in greenhouses, emphasizing accurate sensor-based control for environmental stability. Widiyanto et al. [5] proposed an IoT-based monitoring system that improved data accuracy for agricultural applications. Mayure et al. [6] implemented an Arduino-based irrigation system using moisture thresholds for precise watering. Vaishali et al. [7] introduced a GSM- integrated irrigation model with real-time sensing, enhancing data-driven decision-making. Alexander et al. [8] developed a high-precision medical actuation system, whose methodologies are transferable to nutrient delivery in agriculture. Malde et al. [9] built an automation model for irrigation using logic-based decision control, increasing reliability and precision. Saha et al. [10] uses fuzzy logic and artificial intelligence for erosion mapping helped achieve spatial accuracy. Sheikh et al. [11] designes smart green house system helps to maintain accurate enviornmental factors in the greenhouse system. Ardahan [12] used an setup moisture based irrigation enables precise water delivery. Moustafa et al. [13] used an Arduino setup to imrove fertilization flow, water flow and

to control pests. parinith et al.[14] used data analytics for enhancing precision in environmental control . Shamsihr et al. [15] reviewed automation in greenhouses, emphasizing accurate sensor-based control for environmental stability. Yasinet al.[16] designs remote controlled arduino agriculture system that gives sms alerts and that provide efficient control over the system. Ahsan et al.[17] solar powered automatic gardening system that heps to get real time weather and soil data to improve soil accuracy Parvin et al. [18] developed gyrocope controlled robotic arm for automated tasks that offers real time analysis data and precise actuation. Parvin et al. [19] developed adaptive algorithm to control water pump for accurate water flow. Widiyanto et al. [20] proposed an IoT-based monitoring system that improved data accuracy for agricultural applications and cloud storage for storing the histories. Overall these papers demonstrated effective algorithm to control water flow, fertilizer flow, security system which is more reliable that reduces the costs and improve the quality attributes of agriculture monitoring system

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The proposed system is an automated irrigation solution which uses and arduino uno controller to manage the water flow to the agricultural fields. Includes sensor modules soil moisturize sensor to detect masters in this file and the ultrasonic sensor is used to detect intruders in order to give the security to the agriculture field and the setup is powered by the solar panel which reduces the cost. Includes temperature and humidity sensor in order to give the real time analysis to the farmers. This reduces the manpower and conserve the water to support sustainable farming through the sensors. This uses low power microcontroller programming and efficient circuit design further enhances it's feasibility

Fig. 1. Schematic Diagram

The diagram present in the figure1 shows the schematic diagram of components present in the system.The arduino UNO microcontroller functions as the CPU, it receives the data from the soil moisture sensor and ultrasonic sensor helps to determine the irrigation requirements. When the soil moisture gets dry the arduino analyse the data and the relay get triggered which activates the DC water pump and the solenoid valve that allows controlled water flow to the crops to conserve water. The relay module acts as an electrical switch, ensuring that high-power components such as the pump motor operate safely under the Arduino’s low-power control signals. Additionally, the ultrasonic sensor continuously monitors the water level in the storage tank, preventing the pump from running dry by deactivating it if the water level is too low. The system is solar-powered, making it an environmentally friendly and cost-effective solution for sustainable agriculture. Furthermore, the automated irrigation mechanism operates on a closed-loop feedback system, where real-time sensor readings determine the precise amount of water required, thereby reducing over-irrigation and soil degradation. The integration of embedded systems and renewable energy sources ensures that this system is reliable and can be deployed in areas with limited electricity access. The use of low-power microcontroller programming and efficient circuit design further enhances its feasibility

Fig. 2. Flowchart

The flow chart as shown in the figure 2 describes the algorithm that system follows. At the “START” node. The system initializes the process. arduino collects the data from the moisture sensor whether the soil is dried or not . if it is dry then the relay get triggered and the motor and solenoid turned on and the soil starts wetting when it reaches the adequate level the motor turned off, till it become dry the motor wont turned on , the system runs in a infinite loop.

System Design

The proposed system design is an Arduino-based smart irrigation system powered by a solar panel. It is designed to automate irrigation by monitoring soil moisture levels and controlling the water supply accordingly. The Arduino Uno serves as the central microcontroller, processing data from various sensors and controlling output devices such as the water pump and solenoid valve. A soil moisture sensor is used to detect the moisture level in the soil and sends signals to the Arduino, which then determines whether irrigation is required. Additionally, an ultrasonic sensor is included to measure the water level in a storage tank, ensuring that there is enough water available for irrigation. If this soil remains dry the relay again get triggered the activates the water pump and solenoid valve so the soil recieves adequate amount of water after that the motor will be switched off. Again the process of checking the soil continuous till the system is on. The temperature and humidity sensor send the data to the arduino so the temperature and the humidity is observed through the LCD display so the farmer can take the decisions to cultivate the crops so the algorithm continuous from this start to stop node

Fig. 3. Circuit Diagram

The circuit diagram in the figure 3 shows the circuit connection of proposed system. The relay module is used to control the water pump this relay act as switches at allows the Arduino to turn these components on or off based on the data collected from the sensors. When the soil moisture sensor detects dry soil the Arduino activates the relay to turn on the water pump and open the solenoid valve leads to supplying water to the plants. The ultrasonic sensor continuously monitors the trespessers to find whether they moved in to agriculture field. A solar panel is used as the power source, making the system to use renewable energy that is efficient and environmentally friendly. The solar panel is used to charge a battery to supply power to the Arduino and other components in the system that ensures continuous operation even in the absence of sunlight. This automated irrigation system helps to conserve water by supplying it only when it is needed to the soil to maintain moisture content that reduces waste and

improving efficiency. It is particularly useful for agricultural applications and gardens and areas where water conservation is essential. sensors, relays, and a solar power combination makes the system more sustainable and cost-effective solution for modern irrigation needs.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The system is developed and tested using the flower pot and the embedded components as shown in the figure .the system tests includes two conditions one is at the dry condition and another at wet condition .so we can see the relay condition if it is on water is pumping and it is off water is not flow to the plant

Fig. 4. Hardware setup : relay off condition

- a) a) Figure 4 shows the relay condition which is in off state ,the red light in the relay indicates the off condition. when the wet content in the soil is observed , the moisture sensor sends the signal to arduino to keep relay in the off state . So the motor remains in the off state, and no water flows to the soil. This shows the system is recognizing effectively whether the water is needed or not

Fig. 5. Hardware setup : relay on condition

b) In the figure 5 the green light present in the relay indicates the on condition of the relay. When the soil is dry, the moisture level drops below the preset threshold, prompting the relay to switch ON. Consequently, the motor is activated, allowing water to flow into the pot. This demonstrates the sensor's ability to detect dryness and trigger watering automatically.

The experiment presents the practical benefits of using a moisture sensor and microcontroller. This setup significantly reduces the water waste so it is better setup to conserve the water as it deliver to water only when it is necessary. Instead of using a camera Ultrasonic sensor can be used to detect the intruders. It is also consists of solenoid valve the crops can be protected which prevents this is causes today roots. Since most of the agricultural safety and process is taken over by the embedded system the human intervention gets reduce so the time can be utilized for the other works and productivity can be increased. Furthermore, this experiment shows how the sensors and the controller can be applied to agriculture and garden fields that makes them smarter more efficient and environment friendly. By integrating with the iot a platform remotely can manage they process taking in the agricultural field best and the climate data provided the farmers can take this steps went to plough when to fertilized, when to give vaccination, when to harvest. Based on the climate condition farmers can increase the productivity

V. CONCLUSION

The automatic plant irrigation system developed utilizing Arduino technology provided consistent performance across various soil types during prototype testing. The system incorporates easily accessible electronic components, ensuring both simplicity in deployment and operational efficiency. By automating the irrigation process, it significantly reduces the dependency on labours and optimizes time utilization for farmers, allowing them to allocate efforts to other critical agricultural tasks. A major advantage of this system is its effective water management capability. By delivering water based on real-time soil moisture levels, it eliminates unnecessary water usage, making it an ideal solution for regions facing water scarcity. This precision irrigation approach not only conserves water but also supports optimal crop growth, resulting in improved agricultural productivity and higher yields. The system proves to be a practical, scalable, and sustainable solution for modern farming practices, offering a reliable alternative to traditional manual irrigation methods.

VII. FUTURE SCOPE

The Automatic Plant Water Monitoring System has significant potential for future development and wider applications. With the integration of IoT (Internet of Things), the system can be upgraded to allow remote monitoring and control through a smartphone or web application. This would enable users to track real-time data and manage irrigation from anywhere. Additionally, integrating temperature,

humidity, and light sensors can provide a more comprehensive environmental monitoring solution for precision farming. The system can also be scaled up for use in large-scale agriculture, greenhouses, and vertical farming setups. Machine learning algorithms can be introduced to analyze soil and weather patterns for predictive irrigation scheduling. Moreover, incorporating data storage and cloud connectivity can help in long-term data analysis for improved crop planning and resource management.

VI. REFERENCES

- [1] J. M. Karienyee, G. M. Nduru, J. M. Hubo, and F. E. Ojeyo, "Influence of Rainfall Variability on Tomato Production among Small Scale Farmers in Kieni East Sub County, Kenya," *Journal of Arts and Humanities*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 07–19, Feb. 2019. doi: 10.18533/journal.v8i2.1606.
- [2] Y. D. Setiawan, B. Ghifari, G. Giovan, and M. H. Widiyanto, "Development of IoT-based instrument monitoring application for smart farming using solar as energy source," *Journal of Reconfigurable and Embedded Systems*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 248–259, Jul. 2023. doi: 10.51191/IJRES.V12I2.P248-259.
- [3] S. Yahaya, S. Abubakar, U. Usman, and A. Lado, "Productivity of Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) as affected by Cultivar and Organic amendment in Kano," *Journal of Organic Agriculture and Environment*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 17–24, May 2018.
- [4] R. Shamsihr et al., "Advances in greenhouse automation and controlled environment," *International Journal of Agricultural and Biological Engineering*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 1–22, Jan. 2018. doi: 10.25165/ijabe.20181101.3120.
- [5] M. H. Widiyanto, B. Ghifari, G. Giovan, R. K. Widyaardi, and Y. D. Setiawan, "Development of Internet of Things-Based Instrument Monitoring Application for Farming," in *Proc. 10th Int. Conf. on Cybernetics and Intelligent Systems (ICORIS)*, Oct. 2022, pp. 1–6. doi: 10.1109/ICORIS56026.2022.10034170.
- [6] M. B. Mayure, P. A. Ashirwadam, and A. B. Bagulkar, "Automatic plant watering system," in *2019 Int. Conf. on Vision Towards Emerging Trends in Communication and Networking (ViTECoN)*, 2019, pp. 1–4.
- [7] S. Vaishali, S. Prabhakaran, K. L. Karthick, K. M. Pradeep, and A. G. Abishek, "Mobile integrated smart irrigation management and monitoring system," in *2017 Int. Conf. on Communication and Signal Processing (ICCSP)*, 2017, pp. 2164–2168. doi: 10.1109/ICCSP.2017.8286593.
- [8] R. Alexander, A. Pranav, and C. S. Mahesh, "IoT embedded syringe infusion pump with visual aesthetic dose marker," *Canadian Journal of Anesthesia*, vol. 65, no. 2, pp. 221–222, Feb. 2018. doi: 10.1007/s12630-017-1006-x.
- [9] H. Malde, "IoT based Automated Irrigation and Control System," *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET)*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 6269–6273, 2020.

- [10] S. Saha, M. Pal, P. Nath, and P. Kumar, "Identification of soil erosion-susceptible areas using fuzzy logic and analytical hierarchy process modeling in an agricultural watershed," *Remote Sensing Applications: Society and Environment*, vol. 15, p. 100252, 2019. doi: 10.1016/j.rsase.2019.100252.
- [11] S. S. Sheikh, A. Ahmad, and A. M. Deshmukh, "Automated Smart Irrigation System Using IoT and Cloud Platform," in *IOP Conf. Ser.: Mater. Sci. Eng.*, vol. 414, no. 1, p. 012027, 2018. doi: 10.1088/1757-899X/414/1/012027.
- [12] N. Badal and I. Ardahan, "Application of Internet of Things in smart greenhouse microclimate management for tomato growth," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 1137–1147, Apr. 2021. doi: 10.11591/ijece.v11i2.pp1137-1147.
- [13] J. Prasop, A. Phimpakan, and N. S. Sihabud, "Design of automatic watering system based on Arduino," *Journal of Robotics and Control (JRC)*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 77–82, 2019.
- [14] A. Moustafa, "Using IoT Soil Moisture Sensors for Smart Lettuce Production," *Arab Universities Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, vol. 27, pp. 77–82, 2019.
- [15] J. Muangprathuba, "IoT and agricultural decision support analytics for smart farms," *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, vol. 156, pp. 467–474, 2019. doi: 10.1016/j.compag.2018.12.018.
- [16] H. Yasin, M. S. Zebeara, and M. M. Zebari, "Arduino-based automatic irrigation system: Monitoring and SMS controlling," in *2019 4th Scientific Int. Conference Najaf (SICN)*, 2019.
- [17] M. Ahsan, M. A. Hossain, M. M. Rahman, and M. S. Uddin, "MPPT based Solar Mini Pump Controller Using Perturb and Observe Algorithm," *International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology (IJEAT)*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 2626–2631, 2020. doi: 10.35940/ijeat.C5015.039320.
- [18] T. Tumpa, F. Rahman, S. Chakraborty, and A. Acharjee, "AI-based Smart Gardening and Irrigation System," *International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS)*, vol. 4, no. 6, pp. 152–159, 2020.
- [19] M. Abul-Soud, A. F. M. Sultan, M. M. Hossain, and M. M. Hasan, "Design and implementation of a smart hydroponic greenhouse monitoring system," in *2021 Int. Conf. on Smart Systems and Technologies (SST)*, pp. 142–147. doi: 10.1109/SST51276.2021.9654132.